
Transitions in Libraries upto Artificial Intelligence and its Application

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15544225

Abstract:

India has world's oldest, richest and famous education system. Education without library is a body without soul. In different era of education, various tools and technology applied for promoting education. As per educational demand library change its role in knowledge preservation, organization and dissemination of reading materials. Education is one of the fundamental rights offered by Indian constitution after independence. Ancient universities aimed to train students in fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics and the defense studies. That's why from manuscript age to artificial intelligence age academic libraries face many transitions; artificial intelligence is par excellent to earlier technics. This research paper focuses on it.

Keyword: Artificial Intelligence, Transitions of the library, Academic library, Library Services.

Introduction:

India has rich and oldest education and reading culture. Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing are called four basic skills of language and can be acquired through education only. Education is the only way to acquire knowledge and libraries are a reservoir of the knowledge. Till independence, ancient, Medieval and modern period are the three stages considered in all spheres of progress. Since ancient period in India there were very famous universities. E.g. Nalanda, Takshashila and Amravati were an ancient center for higher learning in India and famous with respect to literature available in these libraries aimed to train to students in fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics and the art of war. Nalanda university was richest and famous for library and which had 09+ million manuscripts

collection. From manuscript age to artificial intelligence age, libraries has faced many transitions. Since ancient period library and library professionals change their role and upgrade themselves as per the era. We are going to split these transitions as per tools and technological changes in India, as manuscript age, prints age, documentation age, information age, Internet age, artificial intelligence.

Transitions of the Library as per tools and technology change:

Library is the gateway to knowledge and culture. Change is the only constant thing in the universe. Such change took place when there is change in technology, generation, new position, job related issues, adaption of something new...etc. change is athree way process, e.g. Happen to you, Happen for you and Happen because of you.

Change always is called as a revolution to the existing system. Library faced such changes and transitions and makes revolution in library system as follows.

- **Manuscript Age:** Before the invention of printing the knowledge was handwritten. Treated as valuable thing and kept in lock. In this age very few persons were achieving the knowledge. Everyone won't have access to library. Librarian supposed to the custodian of knowledge. In this transition librarian has to the play role of caretaker and preservation of library material.
- **Prints Age:** In Germany, around mid-1400s the Gutenberg invented first known mechanized printing press, which initiated the printing revolution. It helps to make multiple copies and publish books in large numbers, to change the role of library and librarian of preservation to dissemination. It helps open access of library to all. Printing age helps in dissemination of knowledge for all.
- **Documentation age:** In this age, libraries were open to all, it increase the usage of library. Society demanded assistance in research to get rapid information of researches going on in other parts of the country or in other countries. In this era, addition to books and periodical begin to publish. It used to describe, explain or instruct regarding some attributes of an object or retrieval of information. Indexing, Abstracting, selective dissemination of information is collectively called documentation. It makes library as documentation center and librarian become documentation officer to assist in research to avoid duplication.
- **Information Age:** In technological age society demands pin pointed Information. Library started information management through computer. Library adapted new storage devices CD rom, Magnetic tape, floppy disk to arouse library space problem. Library is

named as information center and librarian as an information officer. Librarian is engaged in providing right information to the right user at the right time.

- **Internet Age:** It is an information explosion age. Today we are not facing the problem of information scarcity but of information surpluses. Revolution in digitalization and digital materials were exchange all information handling activities. It creates new challenges to LIS professionals. In this changing environment location and adjacency is affected by internet. Library is shifting from building to physical access, physical appearance to virtual, time bound services to round the clock services 24*7 service availability. library within four wall to library without wall, Traditional services to computer and communication services, Todays libraries are known as digital library having digital information stored digitally, can be accessed through internet. Library keeps society updated by providing global information to end user. Internet age gives ability to disseminate digital document and digital information directly to the user.
- **Artificial Intelligence:** Robots help in shelving or managing library, FAQ solve online users query about library and provide correct information and Grok AI will take the place of some services of the library thes all things indicats AI will help library in varies ways. Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing are called four skills of language. Language is the base of literature and literature is the heart of any library. In general The Artificial Intelligence is highly advanced technique and technology for designing software's and robots to think and act intelligently. It enables robots to learn from experience, adapt new inputs, and execute human-like activities. It simulates the human intelligence process through computer

systems and machines. It performs tasks more quickly and effectively than humans.

Components of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and library usage:

Artificial Intelligence helps libraries in daily operations, facilities and tasks more quickly and effectively than humans. There are many components of Artificial Intelligence which can be used in library.

- **Machine Learning:** Robotics, pattern recognition, and chatbots are the examples of the machine learning. It help libraries in the different housekeeping operations and services, from book inventory management, cataloging and information storage and retrieval to user experience and collection management and associated activities
- **Deep Learning:** Image Processing and Neural Networking are examples of AI tools used in the context of Deep Learning. Deep Learning is a machine learning subset. It helps libraries in the different information retrieval mechanism like OPAC searching.
- **Natural Language Processing:** It enables computers to understand, interpret, and generate human language. It helps libraries in the design of subject index, development of information retrieval systems, librametrics and bibliometrics.
- **Pattern Recognition:** It helps libraries in the preservation of archival, managing library image, video databases, book recommendations, improving search functionality, and enhancing resource organization. It helps in online platform to QR code of materials and understand or check if the user is a robot or a human.
- **Robotics:** A robot is a mechanised device that uses artificial intelligence methods to complete automated activities under direct human guidance and pre-defined instructions. It helps

libraries in many ways without humans in various library operations, especially those tasks which are hazardous and time-consuming (Stock verification, shelving, searching, and retrieving information materials from shelves, check-in and check-out). Robots are now being programmed to answer Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) that library patrons may have.

- **Chatbots:** Alexa, Google assistant is the examples of modern chatbots. It referred to as intelligent agents, digital assistants, or virtual agents. It is a software application which can converse intelligently, whether by speech, text, or possibly by embodied expression. It can helps in information retrieval, providing assistance with basic tasks, offering personalized recommendations, and even managing some library services.

Conclusion:

Library is the place where each and every student get connected for resources. Nowadays students are using android mobiles, so they are exposed to more technology in large. That e-literate user's expectation is changed as par era. From transitions like manuscripts, prints and internet, library has changed its ways to provide services to users. In the artificial intelligence age AI brought about new prospects for expanding service areas of the libraries. The application of AI has contributed immensely to the provision and use of library information resources and has helped to achieve the goals and objectives of the library. Library professionals need to cultivate their skills also to optimal use of artificial intelligence and its components.

References:

1. Cox, A. M., Pinfield, S., & Rutter, S. (2019). The intelligent library: Thought leaders' views on the likely impact of artificial intelligence on academic

- libraries. *Library Hi Tech*, 37(3), 418–435. doi:10.1108/LHT-08-2018-0105 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370202124_Applications-of-Artificial-Intelligence-AI-in-Libraries [Accessed Apr 24 2025].
2. Yu, K., Gong, R., Sun, L., & Jiang, C. (2019). The application of artificial intelligence in smart library. *International Conference of Organizational Innovation (ICOI 2019). Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 100, 708-713. 10.2991/icoi-19.2019.124 [Accessed Apr 24 2025].
 3. Oname, I. M., & Alex-Nmecha, J. C. (2020). Artificial intelligence in libraries. In *Managing and Adapting Library Information Services for Future Users*. IGI Global. doi:10.4018/978-1-7998-1116-9.ch008 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370202124_Applications-of-Artificial-Intelligence-AI-in-Libraries. [Accessed Apr 24 2025].
 4. Afolayan, J. O., Ogundokun, R. O., Afolabi, A. G., & Adegun, A. A. (2020). Artificial intelligence, cloud librarianship, and infopreneurship initiatives for Inclusiveness. In *Managing and Adapting Library Information Services for Future Users*. IGI Global. doi:10.4018/978-1-5225-9034-7.ch003 [accessed Apr 24 2025].
 5. Whitehair, K. (2016). Libraries in an Artificially Intelligent World. *Public Libraries*. <http://publiclibrariesonline.org/2016/02/libraries-in-an-artificially-intelligent-world/> [Accessed Apr 24 2025].
 6. Asemi, A., Ko, A., & Nowkarizi, M. (2020). Intelligent libraries: A review on expert systems, artificial intelligence, and robot. *Library Hi Tech*, 39(2), 412–434. doi:10.1108/LHT-02-2020-0038 [Accessed Apr 24 2025].
 7. Jesubukade, E.,(2023) Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Libraries P-73-90 <file:///C:/Users/Comp%20Library/Downloads/Applications-of-Artificial-Intelligence-AI-in-Libraries.pdf> DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-9094-2.ch006 [Accessed Apr 24 2025].